

PATHOLOGY, ORIGIN AND PREVENTION OF HYPERTENSIVE CRISIS

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Complications: Hypertensive crisis is a severe form of arterial hypertension. It can happen at any time. It is observed more often in women than in men. The cause of the incident lies in the violation of blood pressure regulation. If arterial hypertension is common in 40% of the population, then only 1% of cases can have a sharp jump from the basic values, which leads to a sharp deterioration in health with a high risk of death.

Research materials: What are the clear signs of a hypertensive crisis, not only hypertensive patients, but also their relatives should know. Normal and elevated blood pressure values are individual for each person. When a crisis occurs, signs of impaired cerebral or coronary blood supply are observed.

Purpose of the study: Prevention of hypertensive crisis consists in taking antihypertensive drugs regularly. This allows you to monitor the normal level of pressure and the general condition of the patient. If medical recommendations and relevant factors are violated, the function of blood pressure regulation is disturbed, which becomes the main cause of the pathological condition. A significant increase in pressure to values higher than 180-240 mm Hg poses a threat to health and life.

Observed results: The information in this section cannot be used for self-diagnosis and self-treatment. In case of pain or other exacerbation of the disease, diagnostic tests should be prescribed only by the attending physician. You should see your doctor for a diagnosis and to prescribe the right treatment. In order to accurately evaluate the results of your analyzes over time, it is preferable to conduct research in the same laboratory, since different laboratories may use different research methods and units of measurement to perform the same analysis.

Symptoms and signs of their manifestation

When a hypertensive crisis occurs, the following symptoms appear:

nausea, vomiting, suffocation;

convulsions and loss of consciousness;

severe headache;
blurred consciousness and impaired speech and vision;
heart pain and palpitations;
shivering, sweating, shivering;
feeling of lack of air;
Possible loose stools.

Do you have symptoms of a hypertensive crisis?

Only a doctor can accurately diagnose the disease. Do not delay consultation - call +7 (495)

126-13-12

Causes of the development of a serious condition and increased blood pressure

Hypertensive crisis has unique and complex causes:

hormonal disorders;
change in weather conditions;
alcohol consumption;
drinking a lot of coffee;
stop antihypertensive drugs;
stress and depression;
physical stress;
adequate treatment of arterial hypertension.

Summary: Types of hypertensive crisis are classified according to the manifestation of symptoms. Medical care is selected individually according to indications and clinical manifestations. Hypertensive crisis types I and II, complicated and uncomplicated forms are types of pathology. Hyperkinetic crisis or type I is characterized by rapid development. Acute headache and dizziness, nausea and vomiting appear. The state is close to fainting. Blood pressure rises above 200 mm Hg. Art. (systolic - high), therefore red spots appear on the face, neck, chest, feeling of heat, tachycardia, moist skin.

Hypokinetic crisis or type II arterial hypertension occurs in patients of stage III when the treatment regimen or life rhythm is disturbed. The deterioration of well-being develops more slowly, but the intensity remains significant. The severity of the headache increases exponentially. Diastolic (bottom) pressure remains in the range of 140-160 mmHg. Art. Symptoms include nausea and vomiting, lethargy, blurred vision and hearing, and a racing pulse.

Complex hypertensive crisis has several vectors of development, which affect the type of complications. There are the following subtypes: coronary, asthmatic, cerebral. Against this

background, pulmonary edema or cardiac asthma, acute left ventricular failure may develop. Cerebrovascular accidents, ischemic stroke and other pathologies may occur. An uncomplicated hypertensive crisis requires pressure correction within the next 24 hours, but it has an important nuance - there is no risk of damage to target organs.

Diagnosis after diagnosis

The diagnosis of hypertensive crisis is selected depending on the symptoms and type of pathology. Patients are prescribed an ECG. If there are neurological symptoms, computer tomography of the brain is prescribed. This measure is necessary to eliminate swelling. Chest organs are a target for high blood pressure, so monitoring is done using x-rays. Diagnosis is necessary to correctly determine the diagnosis and form of the crisis.

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